

CHEMICAL INVESTIGATION OF THE SEEDS OF *BALANITES ROXBURGII*, PLANCH (HINGORA SEEDS). PART I. SAPONIN

BY V. V. DHEKNE AND B. V. BHIDE

The present work is concerned with the isolation of a fish poison from pericarp of the seeds. The pericarp yields 12% saponin. One in 60,000 parts of the alcoholic extract of the saponin has been found to kill fish. Acetyl and benzoyl derivatives of the sapogenin, obtained on hydrolysis of the saponin with 5% HCl, have been prepared.

Balanites Roxburgii (N. O. Simarubaceae) is found in almost all forests of India. The bark, seeds and leaves are used in Indian medicine. The pericarp is used as a detergent and as a fish poison.

Weil (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1901, 239, 363) showed that the pericarp contains about 7% saponin having the molecular formula $C_{16}H_{26}O_{10}$. Patel (*Curr. Sci.*, 1943, 12, 58) has given the constants of the seed fat. An allied species, *Balanites aegyptica* (Wall) was examined by Kou and Weller (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 800) who isolated the saponin in a crude condition and the sapogenin obtained on hydrolysis was named "Nitogenin". Later Marker (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 1245) showed that this sapogenin must be "Diosgenin". The present work is concerned with the isolation of the fish poison of the pericarp of the seeds.

The seeds were kindly supplied by the Sub-Divisional Forest Officer, Sirsee, and the investigation was financed by the Government of Bombay.

A preliminary investigation showed the absence of alkaloids and that the active principle was probably a saponin. Quantitative estimation showed that the saponin content was 11% on the basis of the weight of the pericarp. Numerous experiments were tried to isolate the saponin in a pure condition. A small quantity of saponin of m.p. 301° was obtained, not pure enough for analysis, but it showed a high haemolytic activity on red blood corpuscles, and fish were killed by alcoholic extract in a concentration of 1 in 60,000. Evidently the fish poison is the saponin. The crude saponin is also lethal to bed bugs.

The saponin on hydrolysis with 5% hydrochloric acid gave the sapogenin (m.p. 197-98°) which was identified as diosgenin by direct comparison by Prof. Marker with an authentic sample. Several attempts were made to identify the sugar part of saponin, but it could not be identified as a large amount of tarry material was obtained with the sugars.

Since diosgenin can be used as a starting material for the preparation of steroid hormones, numerous experiments were carried out to improve the yield of diosgenin from the pericarp, and under best conditions the yield of pure diosgenin was only 0.1%.

EXPERIMENTAL

The pericarp (40 g.) was extracted with different solvents. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Solvent.	Extract.	Solvent.	Extract.
1. Petroleum ether	0.72 %	4. Ethyl acetate	0.67%
2. Ether (sulphuric)	0.23	5. Alcohol	13.82
3. Chloroform	4.65	6. Water	33.2

Examination of the various extracts showed the presence of a saponin. Tests for alkaloids were negative.

Isolation of Crude Saponin.—The pulp from the pericarp of the seeds (100 g.) was Soxhleted with 60% alcohol. The alcohol was distilled off and the extract was acidified with 5% hydrochloric acid. Brownish precipitate was obtained after some time, which was allowed to settle down. The precipitate settled down more rapidly when the acidified extract was diluted with more water. It was very difficult to filter. Hence, it was washed by decantation and finally dewatered by centrifuging and the residue refluxed with absolute alcohol for about half an hour and the alcoholic extract filtered and concentrated. The alcoholic solution was added slowly to about 400 c.c. of ether. A sticky mass was collected at the bottom. The ether layer was decanted off and the residue was washed several times with dry acetone, when a granular solid separated, which was filtered, m.p. 230°. It was again crystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 300-301°. The saponin gave the sapogenin on boiling with 5% hydrochloric acid.

Isolation of Sapogenin.—The pulp from the pericarp of the seeds (1400 g.) was extracted with 60% alcohol by percolation. The alcohol was distilled off and the extract was acidified with 5% hydrochloric acid. A brownish precipitate was obtained after some time, which was allowed to settle down. Dilution of the acidified extract with more water facilitated settling down.

As the precipitate was colloidal in nature it was separated by decantation, washed and finally dewatered by centrifuging. The residue was boiled with 5% hydrochloric acid for about five hours. A solid soon began to separate which was brown at first, but soon darkened. At the end of this period the frothing tendency disappeared. The material obtained was dark and sticky. It was washed several times with water and dried on a filter paper. It was then refluxed for about an hour with ether. The ether dissolved the sapogenin. A dark mass was left which could not be purified. The ether extract on evaporation gave a sticky grey mass, which was crystallised from benzene, followed by one from petrol (charcoal). A sapogenin of m.p. 192-93° was obtained, yield 3 g. The crude sapogenin was crystallised ten times from ethyl alcohol when m.p. rose to 197-99°. Crystallisation from benzene did not raise the melting point any further.

Acetyl Derivative of the Sapogenin.—A mixture of the sapogenin (0.5 g.), fused sodium acetate (1.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) was refluxed for 6 hours and poured in water. After some time the solid separated. It was collected and crystallised from methyl alcohol or benzene in plates, m.p. 191-92°.

Benzoyl Derivative of Sapogenin.—The sapogenin (0.5 g.) was dissolved in pyridine and benzoyl chloride (2 c.c.) was added to it with constant vigorous stirring. The mixture was then heated on a water-bath for half an hour and poured in dilute hydrochloric acid. The solid, separated after keeping overnight, was collected and crystallised from absolute ethyl alcohol or benzene, m.p. 229°.

The following table gives the physical properties of the sapogenin and its derivatives along with those of diosgenin given by other workers. Direct comparison with diosgenin confirmed the identity of this sapogenin.

TABLE I

Name of the compound.	Kon and Weller. (<i>Balanites Aegyptica</i> , Wall. Nitogenin).	Marker <i>et al.</i>	Matsukava* (<i>Dioscorea Takora</i>).	Present work.
(1) Sapogenin	M.p. 201° Sp. rotation: $[\alpha]_D$ -112° Analysis: Found: C, 77.6; H, 10.5. $C_{27}H_{41}O_3$ requires C, 77.8; H, 10.7%.	205°	200° -119° Found: C, 78.2; H, 10.2. $C_{27}H_{41}O_3$ requires C, 78.26; H, 10.14%.	197-199° -118.3° Found: C, 78.12; H, 10.34.
	M.p. 229° Sp. rotation: $[\alpha]_D$ -	238°	237° -	229° -73.82°
(2) Benzoyl derivative	Analysis: Found: C, 78.2; H, 9.1. $C_{34}H_{46}O_4$ requires C, 78.4; H, 9.1%.		Found: C, 78.7; H, 9.0. $C_{34}H_{46}O_4$ requires C, 78.76; H, 8.8%.	Found: C, 79.1; H, 8.4%
	M.p. 191° Sp. rotation: $[\alpha]_D$ -	200°	190° -	190° -172.4°
(3) Acetyl derivative	Analysis: Found: C, 76.1; H, 10. $C_{29}H_{46}O_4$ requires C, 75.9; H, 10.1%.		Found: C, 76.3; H, 9.7. $C_{29}H_{46}O_4$ requires C, 76.3; H, 9.6%.	Found: C, 76.4; H, 9.7%

**J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*,
1936, 58, 408.

MAHARAJA PRATAPSIKH CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
SIR PARASEURAMBHAU COLLEGE,
POONA-2.

Received March 30, 1951.